

Syntheses of Triarylbutanes and Substituted Diaryl Alkanones[†]

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Syntheses of 1,1,4-triarylbutanes, 3-alkyl-3,4-diaryl-butan-2-ones, 3,4-dialkyl-3,4-diaryl-butan-2-ones, 4-alkyl-4,5-diaryl-pentan-3-ones and 4,7-diphenyl-heptan-3-ones have been synthesised as possible antiprogestational agents. A plausible mechanism for the dialkylation in Grignard reaction of α -aryl-cinnamitriles has been proposed.

IN a programme of research aimed towards obtaining non-steroidal antiprogestational agents, it was considered desirable to synthesize 1,1,4-triarylbutanes (1-4), 3-alkyl-3,4-diaryl-butan-2-ones (12-13 & 18-21), *erythro*-3,4-dialkyl-3,4-diaryl-butan-2-ones (14-17), 4-alkyl-4,5-diaryl-pentan-3-ones (5-10 & 22-24) and 4,7-diphenyl-heptan-3-one (11) (Fig. 1, Table 1). These are described in this communication.

Reaction of benzophenone with sodium acetylide followed by the treatment with sulphuric acid yielded diphenyl acrolein which on further reaction with the sodium salt of phenylacetic acid in presence of acetic anhydride, cupric acetate and lead oxide yielded 1,1-diphenyl-4-aryl-1,3-butadienes⁸. Catalytic hydrogenation of these dienes furnished the desired 1,1-diphenyl-4-aryl butanes (1-4). The desired butan-2-ones (12-21), pentane-3-ones (5-10 & 22-24) and heptan-3-one (11) were obtained from substituted benzyl cyanides. The reaction of the latter with substituted benzaldehydes yielded α -aryl cinnamitriles and with cinnamaldehyde yielded α -cinnamylidene- α -tolunitrile. The catalytic hydrogenation of these nitriles furnished α -aryl dihydro-cinnamitriles and 2,5-diphenyl valeronitrile respectively. Reaction of α -aryl cinnamitriles with excess of alkyl magnesium halides in dry ether yielded a mixture of diastereomeric α,β -dialkyl- α,β -diaryl propionitrile¹, the *erythro*-isomer of which on further reaction with methylmagnesium iodide in dry toluene yielded *erythro*-3,4-dialkyl-3,4-diaryl-butan-2-ones (14-17). Grignard reaction of α -aryl dihydrocinnamitriles in dry toluene yielded the desired 3,4-diaryl-butan-2-ones (12-13 and 18-20) and 4,5-diaryl-pentan-3-ones (5-10 & 22) as major products. Alkylation of α -aryldihydro cinnamitriles followed by the Grignard reaction with ethylmagnesium bromide in dry toluene furnished the required 4-alkyl-4,5-diaryl-pentane-3-ones (23-24). A rational explanation to explain the dialkylation in the Grignard reaction of α -aryl cinnamitriles relates to the

mode of addition of the Grignard reagent. Of the two probabilities of addition of alkylmagnesium halide to α -aryl cinnamitriles, the 1,4-addition would alone furnish the β -alkylated derivative while the α,β -dialkylated product may appear from 3,4-addition of the Grignard reagent in two steps. The first step would lead to β -alkylation and the MgX component would then occupy the carbon atom adjacent to the nitrile group. Mechanistically, such a situation would be favoured if the anion gets stabilised on the carbon α to the nitrile group. Since Collins have already shown that the negative charge rests on the adjacent carbon of the nitrile group⁴, the proposed 3,4-addition of the Grignard reagent may be explained. The proposed halomagnesium complex obtained as a result of 3,4-addition of the Grignard reagent could then undergo further coupling reaction with the excess of alkylmagnesium halide present in the reaction mixture possibly by a non-ionic mechanism to yield the α,β -dialkylated derivative. Such a C-C coupling in the Grignard reaction has been reported earlier⁵. The evidence to the formation of a β -alkyl derivative at the beginning of the reaction was obtained by carrying out the Grignard reaction with exactly one mole of alkyl magnesium halide which gave predominantly a β -alkylated derivative (40%) and a minor amount of α,β -dialkylated derivative (0.6%). The formation of the proposed halomagnesium complex was evident from the reaction of alkylmagnesium halide with α -aryldihydrocinnamitriles which furnished the α -alkylated derivative².

Experimental

Catalytic hydrogenation of 1,1-diphenyl-4-aryl butadiene :

The triaryl butadiene (0.002 mole) was hydrogenated in ethanol (15 ml) over 10% Pd-C (60 mg) at 40 lbs/sq. inch for 8 hrs. Usual work-up of the reaction mixture yielded the required compound (1-4) yield 75%.

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL, AND ANALYTICAL, DATA OF VARIOUS KETONES

Comp. No.	R	m.p. (°C)	Molecular formula	Elemental Analysis %	
				Required	Found
1	2	3	4	5	6
1.	<i>o</i> -tolyl	Oil	C ₈ H ₈	C 91.95 H 8.05	91.75 8.25
2.	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	Oil	C ₇ H ₇ Cl	C 82.35 H 6.59	82.10 6.80
3.	<i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl	65-7	C ₈ H ₈ O	C 87.30 H 7.64	87.00 7.90
4.	<i>p</i> -hydroxyphenyl	86-7	C ₇ H ₈ O	C 87.88 H 7.33	87.68 7.72
R ₁ = phenyl, R ₂ = Et					
5.	Phenyl	Oil	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O	C 85.67 H 7.61	85.82 7.40
6.	2,4-dichlorophenyl	Oil	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ O	C 66.46 H 5.25	66.75 5.40
7.	<i>p</i> -tolyl	Oil	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O	C 85.67 H 7.99	85.20 8.18
8.	2,4-dimethoxyphenyl	Oil	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂	C 76.48 H 7.43	76.72 7.25
9.	<i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl	Oil	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂	C 80.56 H 7.51	80.70 7.75
10.	3,4-dichlorophenyl	Oil	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ O	C 66.46 H 5.25	66.82 5.46
11.	Phenethyl	Oil	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O	C 85.67 H 8.32	85.60 8.20
R ₁ = Phenyl, R ₂ = Me					
12.	<i>p</i> -tolyl	Oil	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O	C 85.67 H 7.61	85.75 7.71
13.	2,4-dimethoxyphenyl	Oil	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂	C 76.03 H 7.09	76.40 7.28
R ₁ = Phenyl, R ₂ = R ₃ = R ₄ = Me					
14.	<i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl	Oil	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂	C 80.82 H 7.85	80.55 8.10
15.	2,4-dichlorophenyl	106-7	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ O	C 67.29 H 5.64	67.70 5.85
16.	3,4-dichlorophenyl	Oil	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ O	C 67.29 H 5.64	67.48 5.78
17.	Phenyl	Oil	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O	C 85.67 H 7.99	85.80 8.10
R ₁ = <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl, R ₂ = Me					
18.	<i>p</i> -benzyloxyphenyl	114-15	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ ClO ₂	C 75.71 H 5.80	75.80 5.90
19.	<i>p</i> -(<i>N,N</i> -diethylamino)-ethoxyphenyl	Oil	C ₂₂ H ₂₉ NCLO ₂	C 70.66 H 7.54 N 3.74	70.50 7.70 3.80
20.	<i>m</i> -nitro- <i>p</i> -tolyl	Oil	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ NCLO ₂	C 64.25 H 5.06 N 3.74	64.46 5.20 3.90
R ₁ = Phenyl, R ₂ = R ₃ = Me					
21.	2,4-dimethoxyphenyl	Oil	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂	C 76.48 H 7.43	76.80 7.62
R ₁ = <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl, R ₂ = Et					
22.	Phenyl	Oil	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ClO	C 74.85 H 6.28	75.10 6.52
R ₁ = Phenyl, R ₂ = Et, R ₃ = Me					
23.	Phenyl	Oil	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O	C 85.67 H 7.99	86.00 8.20
R ₁ = Phenyl, R ₂ = Et, R ₃ = <i>n</i> -amyl					
24.	Phenyl	Oil	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ O	C 85.66 H 9.15	85.70 9.36
R ₁ = R ₂ = R ₃ = R ₄ = Nil					
25.	<i>n</i> -amyl	Oil	C ₂₀ H ₂₈ N	C 86.59 H 8.36 N 5.05	86.80 8.66 5.25

Alkylation of α -phenyldihydrocinnamitrile (25) :

To a suspension of sodamide (0.022 mol) in dry ether (40 ml) was added under stirring a solution of the α -phenyldihydrocinnamitrile (0.020 mol) in dry ether (50 ml) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs. It was then cooled in an ice bath and to this was added carefully the amyl bromide (0.04 mole). After the addition was complete the reaction mixture was refluxed for 15 hrs, cooled and was decomposed with dilute HCl. The organic layer was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent distilled off. The residue was purified by column chromatography over silica using hexane as the eluant, yield 70%.

Grignard reaction of α -aryldihydrocinnamitrile :

To a solution of alkylmagnesium halide (0.075 mol) prepared by the reaction of magnesium (0.075 gm atom) and alkyl halide (0.075 mol) in dry ether (50 ml) was added a solution of α -aryldihydrocinnamitrile (0.025 mol) in dry toluene (120 ml). The temperature of the reaction mixture was slowly raised to 100° to drive away the ether present in the mixture. The clear solution was then refluxed for 36 hrs, cooled and decomposed with sulphuric acid (4N). The organic layer was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the removal of the solvent under vacuo followed by repeated chromatography of the residue over silica gel using hexane as the eluant yielded the desired product **12-13**, **18-20** & **5-11**, yield 40-65%. In one case the yield of the α -alkylated ketone (**21**) was more than the yield observed in other cases.

Grignard reaction of α -alkyl- α,β -diaryl propionitrile and erythro- α,β -dialkyl- α,β -diaryl propionitrile :

Following the procedure described above α -alkyl- α,β -diaryl propionitrile yielded the required ketones (**23-24**), yield 60%, while erythro- α,β -dialkyl- α,β -diaryl propionitrile yielded the corresponding erythro ketones (**14-17**), yield 60-70%.

Fig. 1.

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